

EELISA

European University

**REPORT ON EELISA INNOVATION AND CO-CREATION
PROCESSES (2)**

Deliverable 7.2

Date: 31 May, 2024

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EELISA InnoCORE Partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
1	COO	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Technical University of Madrid	UPM	Spain
2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Turkey
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

Alliance members

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Executive summary

This document is prepared within the work package WP7 – “Create the ‘embedding’ for EELISA-wide R & I structures (Optimize outreach)”, as deliverable D7.2 “Report on EELISA innovation and co-creation processes (2)” of the project EELISA INNOVation and COmmon REsearch strategy (hereinafter referred to as EELISA InnoCORE), funded by European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101035811. D7.2 is a follow-up deliverable of D7.1 “Report on EELISA innovation and co-creation processes (1)” that was submitted in November 2022.

EELISA InnoCORE accentuates the full innovation cycle in order to optimize the outcome of its research activities in cooperation with business and civil society. In that regard, we aim not only at offering attractive public events, consulting, and training sessions on innovation processes and co-creation activities, but also at becoming the first European University that can offer test spaces for prototypes to its startups, researchers, and innovators. In order to demonstrate what has been achieved in these domains between December 2022 and May 2024, the document gives an overview of our common EELISA innovation and co-creation activities. We differentiate these activities into two different categories: 1. Consulting and training sessions on innovation processes and on co-creation activities (including joint events on innovation processes and the exchange of best practices for social prototyping); 2. Public events on innovation processes and on co-creation activities (including the running of test spaces for prototypes and projects that also include evaluation of user experiences). The overview covers the second reporting period from December 2022 to May 2024.

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Glossary - Abbreviations and definitions

(alphabetic order)

CA. Consortium Agreement. The consortium agreement is a private agreement between the beneficiaries, to set out the rights and obligations amongst themselves. (It does NOT involve the European Commission/Agency.)

Communication. Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its research outputs to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

Dissemination. The public disclosure of the research outputs by any appropriate means, including by scientific publications in any medium.

Exploitation. The utilisation of research outputs in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

EELISA Community. The EELISA communities are mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

EELISA Cluster. EELISA Clusters are science-based working groups that will work on the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

EELISA Innovation Talks. EELISA Innovation Talks aim to raise the public awareness – and thus also the scientific awareness – for the knowledge generated in EELISA and are publicly visible events and fora for discussion in the real and digital world. The events shall thematise the use of technology and innovation for sustainable development and develop a strong brand of EELISA for a broader public. EELISA Innovation Talks are an event series set up by EELISA InnoCORE.

GA. Grant Agreement. This is the grant contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. It establishes the rights and obligations that govern the grant. It consists of a core text and annexes (for instance, fixing the project content and the project budget).

Project Results/ Project Outputs. By project results we understand a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a project. This includes any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, prototypes, demonstrators, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected. It is not limited to pioneering discoveries, but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior knowledge. Along this document, we use project results and project outputs indistinctively, with the same meaning.

R & I. Research and Innovation

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1 Introduction to EELISA InnoCORE

The European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance (EELISA) is a bottom-up alliance of European higher education institutions representing more than 180,000 students and 50,000 graduates each year, 16,000 faculty members and 11,000 administrative staff. EELISA is one of the 45 European Universities selected by the European Commission under the Erasmus+ call, focused on education. EELISA was selected during the second pilot call. With the formalization of this European University, partners are initiating an unprecedented level of institutionalised cooperation between our institutions in order to gradually achieve our long-term ambitious vision: the education of European Engineers.

A pillar of EELISA will be the setting-up of EELISA Communities: challenge-based working groups where citizens, private companies and academia will collaborate to face societal challenges. EELISA Communities will be the place where education, research, innovation and public debate coexist and connect, enhancing the connection of engineering with society.

Within this framework, **EELISA InnoCORE is conceived as an integral part of the Alliance**, being a tool supporting, strengthening and delving deeper into the cooperation set up by EELISA. Building on the ecosystem of EELISA Communities, **EELISA InnoCORE focuses on the R&I dimension of the Alliance in a three-step plan**: 1) make our researchers and innovators know each other, create spaces for dialogue with citizens and with non-academic actors and set up a portfolio of shared scientific infrastructures; 2) foster and support the development of joint R&I actions and the creation of new structures (research groups, clusters, joint labs, start-ups, scientific parks) and 3) optimize the outreach of these actions.

EELISA InnoCORE will be running for three years and it is structured around seven (7) work packages (WPs), focusing each on one of the key elements of the project. Under InnoCORE, EELISA partners will work on establishing a portfolio of joint research areas and defining a joint roadmap of research infrastructures (WP2). InnoCORE will map existing research infrastructures and facilities (WP4), with two aims: establishing the rules for opening their use and defining the main features of a booking system so that these resources can be used by all researchers of the Alliance, on the one hand; eventually, establishing a framework for jointly investing in new infrastructures.

EELISA InnoCORE will support the collaboration and the setting-up of joint research projects among the members of the Alliance through the development of a networking platform (WP5), the setting-up of clusters¹, the launching of seed funding for prospective young researchers (WP5) and the use of existing or new equipment and facilities in labs to foster collaborations (WP4). In addition to this, EELISA InnoCORE has two work packages dedicated to interlinking the incubation, start-up and entrepreneurship support services of the members of the alliance (WP7) and to foster the participation of society in science (WP7) and strengthening relations with the industry world (WP6). UPM will coordinate and lead the management of the project,

¹ Science-based working groups that will work on scientific and technological solutions than can help solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

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being responsible for guiding the project in cross-cutting issues, such as gender balance (WP1). Lastly, the project has a dedicated work package on open science (WP3).

WP	WP title	WP Leader
WP1	Coordination, evaluation, communication and dissemination	UPM
WP2	EELISA Research and Innovation Strategy	ITÜ
WP3	EELISA Strategic Framework for Open Science practices	UPB
WP4	EELISA Multi Labs (sharing facilities & equipment)	PSL
WP5	Set up initiatives for joint research projects (Enable joint research)	SNS
WP6	Reinforcing cooperation in R&I with other sectors, especially academia-business cooperation	BME
WP7	Create the "embedding" for EELISA-wide R&I structures (Optimize outreach)	FAU

Table 1: List of work packages and WP leaders

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2 General Considerations

According to the EELISA InnoCORE Grant Agreement, deliverable 7.2 “Report on EELISA innovation and co-creation processes (2)” gives an “[o]verview of consulting and training sessions and public events held on innovation process and on co-creation activities across the EELISA network with a documentation of test spaces run, number of citizens involved and a summary of social prototyping evaluations (starting in year two)”. In the corresponding and more detailed description of EELISA InnoCORE task 7.1 “Interaction platforms and citizen science” it is stated that “we will offer EELISA-wide consulting, trainings and joint events on innovation processes, exchange best practices for social prototyping and run test spaces for prototypes and projects that also include evaluation of user experiences.” The rationale behind these activities is that we want to “accentuate the full innovation cycle in order to optimize the outcome of [our] research activities in cooperation with business and civil society. One important cornerstone for this are (mainly physical) interaction platforms – innovation hubs in all our partner cities that are open to everyone interested in scientifically based co-creation.” The description of T7.1 continues that “[a]s one of the most innovative universities in Europe, FAU can bring to bear its wide experience and its comprehensive innovation ecosystem, for instance in its long-standing collaboration with Fraunhofer IIS or in particular with the open innovation lab JOSEPHS in Nuremberg.” In the course of the EELISA InnoCORE project, it turned out that JOSEPHS, the open innovation lab in Nuremberg’s city center, is even more important for the implementation of task 7.1 than we initially would have assumed. This is because JOSEPHS, as part of FAU’s innovation ecosystem, is the only institution in the EELISA innovation ecosystem through which we can offer test spaces for prototypes to our startups, researchers and innovators. In the end, this may come as no surprise, as JOSEPHS is unique in its kind in Germany and probably also in Europe. Additionally, these EELISA test spaces at JOSEPHS were also necessary for co-creation activities, social prototyping evaluations, and the evaluation of user experiences.

From this point of departure, we made the plan to make a virtue of necessity and to become the first European University that can offer test spaces for prototypes to its startups, researchers and innovators. The means of our choice to achieve this aim was to organize two EELISA Prototype Contests open to our startups, researchers and innovators. If funding allows, this activity established by EELISA InnoCORE will be continued in EELISA phase II WP10. The winning prototypes of the two EELISA Prototype Contests each received an EELISA test space at JOSEPHS in the city center of Nuremberg (and the best prototypes from each EELISA partner got a co-creation workshop with the innovation experts from JOSEPHS). Thus, many visitors (more than 250) could directly test the winning prototypes in the two EELISA test spaces and their user experiences were professionally evaluated. The winning startups got important feedback about their prototype, which greatly helped them to improve their prototype and to get important information about their potential customers. Potentially, thousands of visitors could also see the winning prototypes in the EELISA test spaces and got to know about EELISA InnoCORE and the European University project. Furthermore, the open calls had the effect of disseminating open innovation practices among all members of the Alliance. Last but not least, this activity helped to strengthen the innovative potential of our European University EELISA and can serve as a best practice model for other European

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Universities. We are sure that by having launched this activity, we have not only increased the attractiveness of EELISA InnoCORE among our startups, researchers and innovators as well as among the general public, but also built an innovation model for European Universities. To co-finance this activity we have received funding from the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research and the German Academic Exchange Service (DAAD).

In addition to our innovation and co-creation activities around the first and second EELISA Prototype Contest with the EELISA test spaces, we have also offered public events, consulting, and training sessions on innovation processes and on co-creation activities (including joint events on innovation processes and the exchange of best practices for social prototyping). In the following, this deliverable gives an overview of these various activities. The first part of the following chapter gives an overview of consulting and training sessions on innovation processes and on co-creation activities (including joint events on innovation processes and the exchange of best practices for social prototyping). The second part of the following chapter gives an overview of public events on innovation processes and on co-creation activities (including the running of test spaces for prototypes and projects that also include evaluation of user experiences). This overview covers the second reporting period from December 2022 to May 2024.

3 Overview of EELISA innovation and co-creation activities

This chapter gives an overview of EELISA innovation and co-creation activities during the second reporting period, from December 2022 to May 2024. The first part of the chapter concentrates on consulting and training sessions on innovation processes and on co-creation activities (including joint events on innovation processes and the exchange of best practices for social prototyping). Various activities have taken place in this domain during the second reporting period. The second part of the chapter will give an overview of public events on innovation processes and on co-creation activities (including the running of test spaces for prototypes and projects that also include evaluation of user experiences). Most notable among these activities and among our EELISA innovation and co-creation activities in general are the first and second EELISA Prototype Contest.

3.1 Consulting and training sessions on innovation processes and on co-creation activities (including joint events on innovation processes and the exchange of best practices for social prototyping)

In the second reporting period from December 2022 to May 2024, EELISA InnoCORE WP7 offered various consulting and training sessions on innovation processes and on co-creation activities (including joint events on innovation processes and the exchange of best practices

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for social prototyping) via EELISA media channels for innovation to EELISA students, startups, researchers, innovators, and staff. The following will be an overview of these activities.

3.1.1 “SABG – The Sant’Anna Business Game” offered by SSSA

Name of the activity	SABG – The Sant’Anna Business Game
Short description of the activity	JEBE is the Junior Enterprise run by students of Sant’Anna School of Advanced Studies. It was created to offer the School’s academic excellence to the business world. We provide companies various consulting services and we entirely reinvest our profits in workshops and training courses. JEBE is a member of the JEE Alliance, that works to represent, develop and integrate the European Junior Enterprises. This year JEBE is organizing, for the first time since the Covid crisis, its Business Game, that is part of the Alliance of European Business Games: JEBE’s partner companies present them some challenges, some business cases similar to the problems that their real-life employees have to solve and JEBE allows students to test their capabilities and compete among each other to provide the best solution. HR recruiters from JEBE’s partner companies view the CVs of the selected students, supervise the game and often use the challenges as a means of evaluation, taking the best participants in consideration for internship or even job offers. Through selecting participants and through the business game itself, JEBE is willing to recognise exceptional talents. Participation for EELISA students is possible and scholarships can be provided.
Location of the activity (address, if online: link)	Sant’Anna School of Advanced Studies Event webpage: https://eelisa.eu/events/sabg-the-santanna-business-game/ and https://businessgame2022.jebesantanna.it/
Type of activity	Workshop
Target group	Students
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	The applications, which are the CVs and pictures of the applicants, need to be sent to info@businessgame.jebesantanna.it before 31 October 2022. For more information, see https://businessgame2022.jebesantanna.it/
Application deadline	31 October 2022
Date of the activity	25-26 November 2022
Number of participants	61 (No data could be reported in in D7.1, therefore it is now reported here.)
Number of participants from EELISA partners	2 from ENPC, 7 from FAU, 1 from ITU, 5 from SNS, and 46 from SSSA (No data could be reported in D7.1, therefore is now reported here.)

Table 2: “SABG – The Sant’Anna Business Game” offered by SSSA

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3.1.2 EELISA InnoCORE WP7 meetings on innovation and co-creation activities offered by EELISA InnoCORE WP7

Name of the activity	EELISA InnoCORE WP7 meetings on innovation and co-creation activities
Short description of the activity	During the second reporting period, we held several EELISA InnoCORE WP7 Meetings, in which we exchanged best practices for social prototyping, planned common activities and events, discussed the idea of the EELISA Prototype Contests, and agreed on launching the Call for the Second EELISA Prototype Contest. For a list of the experts and representatives from EELISA partners who participated in the meetings cf. p. 5 of this document.
Location of the activity (address, if online: link)	Zoom meetings and on-site meeting in Istanbul
Type of activity	Work package meetings
Target group	WP7 representatives and innovation experts of each EELISA partner
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	Not necessary, as all participants were invited.
Application deadline	None
Date and time of the activity	13 February 2023, 10:00-11:00 (CET), 11 July 2023, 10:45-11:30 (Istanbul time), and 4 December 2023, 16:00-17:00 (CET)

Table 3: EELISA InnoCORE WP7 meetings on innovation and co-creation activities offered by EELISA InnoCORE WP7

3.1.3 First EELISA Co-Creation Workshop at JOSEPHS offered by FAU

Name of the activity	First EELISA Co-Creation Workshop at JOSEPHS
Short description of the activity	In the First EELISA Prototype Contest, the applicants with the best prototypes from each EELISA partner got a co-creation workshop with JOSEPHS' open innovation experts. The workshop was a two day (hybrid) open innovation and co-creation methods coaching that helped the startups to make the next steps towards successful market entry with their prototypes.
Location of the activity (address, if online: link)	JOSEPHS – The Open Innovation Lab, Nuremberg, Germany and online via Zoom
Type of activity	Co-creation workshop
Target group	Startups that want to bring their prototypes to the market (and who participated in the first EELISA prototype contest), experts from EELISA

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	partners' technology transfer offices, and EELISA InnoCORE WP7 representatives
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	Applicants had to use the application form for the First EELISA Prototype Contest that is available on the event webpage: https://eelisa.eu/events/call-for-the-first-eelisa-prototype-contest/
Application deadline	18 November 2022
Date of the activity	17 and 18 March 2023
Number of participants	9
Number of participants from EELISA partners	2 from ITU, 2 from UPM, 2 from FAU, 1 from SSSA (and 2 from JOSEPHS)

Table 4: First EELISA Co-Creation Workshop at JOSEPHS offered by FAU

3.1.4 EELISA PhD Innovation Day offered by FAU

Name of the activity	EELISA PhD Innovation Day
Short description of the activity	EELISA InnoCORE and FAU's Startup Consulting Services organized an innovation day open for PhD students from EELISA partners that highlighted career options in the startup world. The EELISA PhD Innovation Day included workshops on ideation, an info session about patent management, and workshops with PhDs who already successfully founded their own startup.
Location of the activity (address, if online: link)	ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator, Nuremberg EELISA Event Webpage: https://eelisa.eu/events/join-the-phd-innovation-day-at-fau/
Type of activity	Ideation workshop
Target group	PhD students from EELISA partners
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	https://www.eelisa.fau.de/fau_pid/
Application deadline	13 March 2023
Date of the activity	27 March 2023
Number of participants	41

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Number of participants from EELISA partners	28 from FAU, 7 from UPB, 1 from BME (and 2 from Acalta, 1 from Hydrogenious, 1 from DuLog, 1 from ZOLLHOF)
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Table 5: EELISA PhD Innovation Day offered by FAU

3.1.5 “Change makers: Shaping the future” offered by UPM

Name of the activity	Change makers: Shaping the future
Short description of the activity	Join the course “Change makers: Shaping the future” and learn to succeed in the rapidly evolving online world. In this practical course, you will discover tools and methodologies for innovators, based on new developments and opportunities presented in this new era. Participants will work in teams and develop a real project with guidance from experienced entrepreneurs and academics. It will be held online through the platform Zoom from November 2nd to November 30th. The schedule for the fall semester is every Tuesday and Thursday from 2:30 p.m. to 5:30 p.m. and 2:30 p.m. to 5 p.m. CET respectively. Students are requested to interact during the lessons, work in teams, complete tasks, read the references assigned, and provide results for the assignments. All materials will be available online upon the start. In addition to class, the students will be encouraged to participate in innovation/leadership/entrepreneurship-related events that will be announced during the class. This is an entrepreneurship activity of the EELISA innoCORE project.
Location of the activity	Online via Zoom EELISA Event Webpage: https://eelisa.eu/events/change-makers-shaping-the-future-training-session-i-into-the-pitch/
Type of activity	Innovation and entrepreneurship course (This activity is also reported as an EELISA entrepreneurship activity in D7.4 Evaluation of joint entrepreneurial activities.)
Target group	Students
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	https://educadn.typeform.com/to/SlqUNzHJ?typeform-source=eelisa.eu
Application deadline	1 November 2023
Date of the activity	2 – 30 November 2023, Tuesday 2:30-5:30 pm and Thursday 2:30-5:00 pm (CET)
Number of participants	304 participants

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Number of participants from EELISA partners	81 from UPM, 4 from ITU, 4 from UPB, 2 from FAU, 2 from SNS, 1 from BME
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Table 6: “Change makers: Shaping the future” offered by UPM

3.1.6 “Sant’Anna Business Game 2023” offered by SSSA

Name of the activity	Sant’Anna Business Game 2023
Short description of the activity	<p>Sant’Anna Business Game is a great chance to extend your network, being in touch with 70 smart students from Italy, Europe and the whole world. The partner companies will present challenges and business cases similar to the problems that their real-life employees have to solve. In this context, the students can test their capabilities and compete among each other to provide the best solution. You will also have access to interviews with our sponsors, both main and basic and the winners will have privileged contact with the human resources of the main sponsors. Among them, you will find Bain&Co and Generali.</p> <p>About JEBE: JEBE is the Junior Enterprise run by students of Sant’Anna School of Advanced Studies. It was created to offer the School’s academic excellence to the business world. We provide companies various consulting services and we entirely reinvest our profits in workshops and training courses. JEBE is a member of the JEE Alliance, that works to represent, develop and integrate the European Junior Enterprises. HR recruiters from our partner companies view the CVs of the selected students, supervise the game and often use the challenges as a means of evaluation, taking the best participants in consideration for internship or even job offers. Through selecting participants and through the business game itself, we are willing to recognise exceptional talents.</p>
Location of the activity (address, if online: link)	Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna in Pisa, Italy
Type of activity	Business Game
Target group	Students from all EELISA partners
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	<p>https://businessgame2023.jebesantanna.it/#Enroll</p> <p>(Participation requirements: Participants must be enrolled as students at one of the EELISA partner universities.)</p>
Application deadline	16 November 2023
Date of the activity	24 and 25 November 2023

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Number of participants	70
Number of participants from EELISA partners	No data available

Table 7: “Sant’Anna Business Game 2023” offered by SSSA

3.1.7 Second EELISA Co-Creation Workshop at JOSEPHS offered by FAU

Name of the activity	Second EELISA Co-Creation Workshop at JOSEPHS
Short description of the activity	In the Second EELISA Prototype Contest, the applicants with the best prototypes from each EELISA partner got a co-creation workshop with JOSEPHS’ open innovation experts. The workshop was a two day (hybrid) open innovation and co-creation methods coaching that helped the startups to make the next steps towards successful market entry with their prototypes. For further information, see the following report about the event: https://eelisa.eu/improving-start-ups-second-eelisa-josephs-co-creation-workshop/
Location of the activity (address, if online: link)	JOSEPHS – The Open Innovation Lab, Nuremberg, Germany and online via Zoom
Type of activity	Co-creation workshop
Target group	Startups that want to bring their prototypes to the market and who participated in the Second EELISA Prototype Contest: The call was open to startups, researchers, and innovators from all EELISA institutions (including startups founded in the last five years by alumni of EELISA institutions and startups from the following incubators connected to EELISA institutions: actúaupm (UPM), BME U[S]3 (BME), Chimie Paris Innov (PSL), Incubateur Descartes (ENPC), Incubateur Paris-Dauphine (PSL), Innovation Labs (UPB), ITU Cekirdek (ITU), ITU Ginova (ITU), PC Up (PSL), Polo Tecnologico di Navacchio (SNS), Station F (ENPC), ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator (FAU)). Applicants should have had a clear intention to develop their prototype (or prototype idea) into a high-quality product ready for successful market entry in Europe. Applications from all disciplines were welcome, with a preferred relation to innovation, technical solutions, and the Sustainable Development Goals. (Note: Winners of the first EELISA prototype contest were not eligible to apply again, in order to give other startups, researchers, and innovators the opportunity to benefit from the contest.)
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	Applicants had to use the application form for the Second EELISA Prototype Contest that is available on the event webpage: https://eelisa.eu/events/call-for-the-second-eelisa-prototype-contest/

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Application deadline	27 October 2023
Date of the activity	8 and 9 December 2023
Number of participants	22
Number of participants from EELISA partners	14 from FAU, 3 from ITU, 1 from BME, 1 from ENPC (and 3 from JOSEPHS)

Table 8: Second EELISA Co-Creation Workshop at JOSEPHS offered by FAU

3.2 Public events on innovation processes and on co-creation activities (including the running of test spaces for prototypes and projects that also include evaluation of user experiences)

In the second reporting period from December 2022 to May 2024, EELISA InnoCORE WP7 offered several public events on innovation processes and on co-creation activities (including the running of test spaces for prototypes and projects that also include the evaluation of user experiences) via EELISA media channels for innovation to EELISA students, startups, researchers, innovators, and staff. We asked EELISA partners to offer relevant events via EELISA media channels for innovation to the entire EELISA European University. Moreover, and most notably, we have organized two EELISA Prototype Contests open to EELISA startups, researchers and innovators (and the number of applications increased by 100% from the first to the second EELISA Prototype Contest). The following will be an overview of these public events on innovation processes and on co-creation activities.

3.2.1 “First EELISA Test Space at JOSEPHS for the Winner of the First EELISA Prototype Contest” offered by FAU

Name of the activity	First EELISA Test Space at JOSEPHS for the Winner of the First EELISA Prototype Contest
Short description of the activity	The EELISA innoCORE project pursues the ambitious goal to transform EELISA into the first European University that can offer test spaces for prototypes to its startups, researchers, and innovators. To promote this goal, EELISA innoCORE calls for participation in the first EELISA prototype contest. The winner of the first EELISA prototype contest will get the EELISA test space at JOSEPHS – The Open Innovation Lab (worth 15,000 €). This will include efficient onboarding and custom fit research design, all-round care by JOSEPHS’ innovation specialists, a minimum of one month of actual testing with at least 100 potential customers for 20 minutes each, interim results and adjustments if necessary, a detailed final report with results and impulses for action, honest feedback of your potential customers, an

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	<p>unbiased view from the outside (JOSEPHS as a neutral entity), well-founded facts for internal decision making, access to a long-standing expertise in open innovation and co-creation, and the possibility of white label tests. For further information, see the event webpage and the call document: https://eelisa.eu/events/call-for-the-first-eelisa-prototype-contest/ and https://eelisa.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/Call-for-the-First-EELISA-Prototype-Contest-OK.pdf.</p>
Location of the activity (address, if online: link)	JOSEPHS – The Open Innovation Lab, Nuremberg, Germany
Type of activity	Public event on innovation process and co-creation activity: First EELISA Test Space at JOSEPHS for the winner of the first EELISA Prototype Contest
Target group	The call for the First EELISA Prototype Contest was open to startups, researchers, and innovators from all EELISA institutions (including startups founded by alumni of EELISA institutions who could apply up to five years after the founders graduated). Applicants should have had a clear intention to develop their prototype into a high-quality product ready for successful market entry in Europe. Applications from all disciplines were welcome, with a preferred relation to innovation, technical solutions, and Sustainable Development Goals. The target group of the First EELISA Test Space itself was the general public in the city center of Nuremberg.
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	Applicants had to use the application form for the First EELISA Prototype Contest that is available on the event webpage: https://eelisa.eu/events/call-for-the-first-eelisa-prototype-contest/
Application deadline	<p>18 November 2022</p> <p>The poster features the EELISA logo and text: 'Call for the First EELISA Prototype Contest', 'Win the EELISA test space (worth 15.000 €) and a workshop at JOSEPHS!!', and 'Submit your proposal by November 18th, 2022!'. It includes an illustration of a person at a computer and another person standing next to a lightbulb.</p>
Number of applications	5 applications (2 from UPM, 1 from ITU, 1 from UPB, 1 from FAU)
Dates of the activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 28 November 2022: Jury meeting to select the winner of the First EELISA Prototype Contest: The winner was Dr. Adán Sánchez from UPM with his nature-based air purifier. - 1 December 2022: Online kick-off meeting to plan the first EELISA Test Space at JOSEPHS

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 12 December 2022: The kick-off workshop with the winning prototype of the First EELISA Prototype Contest, a nature-based air purifier developed by the startup “The Green Factor” from UPM that addresses the problem of air pollution, was held in presence at JOSEPHS. During the workshop the design of the co-creation process in the first EELISA Test Space and the design of the Test Space were developed. - Mid-December 2023: The first EELISA Test Space was set up at JOSEPHS and was open for the general public until early February 2023. 113 user experiences of the winning prototype were professionally evaluated in co-creation processes. The first EELISA Test Space was of great interest to the visitors at JOSEPHS. - 20 January 2023: A meeting for presenting and discussing the interim results of the EELISA Test Space and to make some adjustments based on the experiences of the first testing period. - 30 January 2023: After various preparations including a preparatory meeting at JOSEPHS on 26 January 2023 and the conception of a script, the video shooting about the first EELISA Test Space took place at JOSEPHS. (After several feedback loops, the final video was uploaded on the EELISA YouTube channel on 11 April 2023: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Pq08TYa-A_I) - 15 February 2023: Final meeting for the presentation and discussion of the final report of the results of the first EELISA Test Space and impulses for action.
<p>Documentation of the test space</p>	<p>Link to the YouTube video about the first EELISA Test Space at JOSEPHS: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Pq08TYa-A_I</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> </div>

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Number of citizens involved	<p>113</p> <p>(From 20 December 2022 to 31 January 2023, 113 people were qualitatively interviewed in the first EELISA Test Space where they engaged in a co-creation process and their user feedback and experiences were evaluated by JOSEPHS open innovation specialists.)</p>
Summary of social prototyping evaluations	<p>After the presentation of the final report of results of the first EELISA Test Space and of the impulses for action on 15 February 2023, an interview with Adán Sánchez, the winner of the first EELISA prototype contest, was conducted and published on the EELISA website: https://eelisa.eu/meet-dr-adan-sanchez-winner-of-the-first-eelisa-prototype-contest/. (Note: The 35 pages final presentation of results and impulses for action that was created by JOSEPHS open innovation experts for the winner of the first EELISA Test Space is confidential and will not be reproduced in this public deliverable.)</p>

Table 9: “First EELISA Test Space at JOSEPHS for the Winner of the First EELISA Prototype Contest” offered by FAU

3.2.2 “Second EELISA Test Space at JOSEPHS for the Winner of the Second EELISA Prototype Contest” offered by FAU

Name of the activity	<p>Second EELISA Test Space at JOSEPHS for the Winner of the Second EELISA Prototype Contest</p>
Short description of the activity	<p>The EELISA innoCORE project pursues the ambitious goal to transform EELISA into the first European University that offers test spaces for prototypes to its startups, researchers, and innovators. To promote this goal, EELISA innoCORE calls for participation in the second EELISA prototype contest. The winner of the second EELISA prototype contest will get an EELISA test space at JOSEPHS – The Open Innovation Lab (worth 15,000 €). This will include efficient onboarding and custom fit research design, all-round care by JOSEPHS’ innovation specialists, a minimum of one month of</p>

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	<p>actual testing with at least 100 potential customers for 20 minutes each, interim results and adjustments if necessary, a detailed final report with results and impulses for action, honest feedback of your potential customers, an unbiased view from the outside (JOSEPHS as a neutral entity), well-founded facts for internal decision making, access to a long-standing expertise in open innovation and co-creation, and the possibility of white label tests. For further information, see the event webpage and the call document: https://eelisa.eu/events/call-for-the-second-eelisa-prototype-contest/ and file:///C:/Users/spuwschk/Downloads/Call-for-the-Second-EELISA-Prototype-Contest-3-1.pdf.</p>
Location of the activity (address, if online: link)	JOSEPHS – The Open Innovation Lab, Nuremberg, Germany
Type of activity	Public event on innovation process and co-creation activity: Second EELISA Test Space at JOSEPHS for the winner of the second EELISA Prototype Contest
Target group	<p>The call was open to startups, researchers, and innovators from all EELISA institutions (including startups founded in the last five years by alumni of EELISA institutions and startups from the following incubators connected to EELISA institutions: actúaupm (UPM), BME U[S]3 (BME), Chimie Paris Innov (PSL), Incubateur Descartes (ENPC), Incubateur Paris-Dauphine (PSL), Innovation Labs (UPB), ITU Cekirdek (ITU), ITU Genova (ITU), PC Up (PSL), Polo Tecnologico di Navacchio (SNS), Station F (ENPC), ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator (FAU)). Applicants should have had a clear intention to develop their prototype (or prototype idea) into a high-quality product ready for successful market entry in Europe. Applications from all disciplines were welcome, with a preferred relation to innovation, technical solutions, and the Sustainable Development Goals. (Note: Winners of the first EELISA prototype contest were not eligible to apply again, in order to give other startups, researchers, and innovators the opportunity to benefit from the contest.)</p>
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	<p>Applicants had to use the application form for the Second EELISA Prototype Contest that is available on the event webpage: https://eelisa.eu/events/call-for-the-second-eelisa-prototype-contest/</p>

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Application deadline	27 October 2023 <p>Call for the Second EELISA Prototype Contest</p> <p>Win the EELISA test space worth 15.000 € and the EELISA co-creation workshop at JOSEPHS!</p> <p>Submit your proposal by October 27th, 2023!</p>
Number of applications	10 applications (4 from FAU, 3 from UPM, 1 from BME, 1 from ENPC, 1 from ITU)
Dates of the activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 7 November 2023: Jury meeting to select the winner of the Second EELISA Prototype Contest: The winners were Pauline Nöldemann and Yannick Wiesner from FAU, with their digital health app BesserEsser. - 16 November 2023: Online kick-off meeting to plan the second EELISA Test Space at JOSEPHS - 20 November 2023: The kick-off workshop with the winners of the Second EELISA Prototype Contest, Pauline Nöldemann and Yannick Wiesner from the startup BesserEsser, JOSEPHS' open innovation experts and David Schkade as the organizer of the Second EELISA Prototype Contest took place in presence at JOSEPHS. During the workshop the design of the co-creation process in the second EELISA Test Space and the design of the Test Space were developed. - 7 December 2023: The second EELISA Test Space was set up at JOSEPHS and was open for the general public until early February 2024. 138 user experiences of the winning prototype were professionally evaluated in co-creation processes. The second EELISA Test Space was of great interest to the visitors at JOSEPHS. - 8 and 9 December 2023: The participants of the second EELISA co-creation workshop at JOSEPHS had the chance to visit the second EELISA Test Space. - 10 January 2024: A workshop was held at JOSEPHS to present the interim results of the second EELISA Test Space and to make some adjustments of the test space based on the experiences of the first testing period. - 19 January 2024: A reel about the second EELISA Test Space was published on Instagram: Click here. - 9 February 2024: Final meeting for the presentation and discussion of the final report of the results of the second EELISA Test Space and impulses for action.
Documentation of the test space	Link to the Instagram reel about the second EELISA Test Space at JOSEPHS: Click here.

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<p>Number of citizens involved</p>	<p>138</p> <p>(In December 2023 and January 2024, 138 people were qualitatively interviewed in the first EELISA Test Space where they engaged in a co-creation process and their user feedback and experiences were evaluated by JOSEPHS open innovation specialists.)</p>
<p>Summary of social prototyping evaluations</p>	<p>After the presentation of the final report of results of the second EELISA Test Space and of the impulses for action on 9 February 2024, an interview with Pauline Nöldemann and Yannick Wiesner, the winners of the second EELISA prototype contest, was conducted and published on the EELISA website: https://eelisa.eu/80-percent-of-the-young-target-group-would-use-our-app-an-interview-with-pauline-noldemann-and-yannick-wiesner-about-the-besseresser-eelisa-testspace-at-josephs/. (Note: The 51 pages final presentation of results and impulses for action that was created by JOSEPHS open innovation experts for the winners of the second EELISA Test Space is confidential and will not be reproduced in this public deliverable.)</p>

Table 10: “Second EELISA Test Space at JOSEPHS for the Winner of the Second EELISA Prototype Contest” offered by FAU

3.2.3 “The Role of Venture Capital in the Innovation Process: Examples from Turkey and Eastern Europe” offered by ITU

<p>Name of the activity</p>	<p>The Role of Venture Capital in the Innovation Process: Examples from Turkey and Eastern Europe</p>
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Short description of the activity	Venture Capital (VC) firms represent key stakeholders in the innovation ecosystem. By providing equity for technology driven entrepreneurial firms in the early stages, they fuel high speed growth and help building competitive advantage. The panel will not only address how VC firms scout, select and deal with technology driven startups, but also try to uncover the value-added activities following the post-investment process. In an increasingly globalized market for capital, the panel will furthermore debate the degree to which early-stage startup deals are context-bound. Additionally, panelists will discuss whether the degree of radical innovations made by startups matter in closing a deal with the VC firms as well as the factors, which influence early-stage valuations. For further information, see the event webpage: https://eelisa.eu/events/innovation-talk-7-the-role-of-venture-capital-in-the-innovation-process-examples-from-turkey-and-eastern-europe/ .
Location of the activity (address, if online: link)	Suleyman Demirel Cultural Center (SDKM), İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi (ITU), Ayazağa, Istanbul and on the EELISA YouTube Channel: Click here .
Type of activity	EELISA Innovation Talk (This event is also reported in EELISA InnoCORE D7.7 as EELISA Innovation Talk # 7.)
Target group	Entrepreneurs, researchers, European students, incubation centers, angel investors, and the general public who is interested in entrepreneurship and technology based innovations
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	No registration required
Application deadline	None
Date of the activity	11 January 2023
Number of participants	40
Number of participants from EELISA partners	No data available

Table 11: “The Role of Venture Capital in the Innovation Process: Examples from Turkey and Eastern Europe” offered by ITU

3.2.4 “Female Innovation” offered by FAU

Name of the activity	Female Innovation
Short description of the activity	EELISA, Siemens, and Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU) cordially invite you to this EELISA Innovation Talk on

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	<p>the topic of “Female Innovation”. The talk will be an exchange with successful female innovators who will share their experiences and views about “Female Innovation” and provide motivation, tips, and tricks for career advancement. The event is intended to be easily accessible to everyone interested in the topic and aims to provide a lasting impulse for your personal development.</p> <p>What’s in for you?</p> <p>When it comes to innovation, women have great contributions to make. However, in the real world of innovation, be it in STEM careers, startups, or venture capital, women are still in the minority and a great deal of innovation potential is lost as a result. Why is that? What can be done about it? And how can female innovators nevertheless be successful? In this EELISA Innovation Talk, we will shed light on these questions highlighting different perspectives from successful female innovators who will share their experiences and give insights into their career paths, innovation experience, and views on female innovation. The audience will have the opportunity to ask their questions to the speakers and after the panel discussion, we will also have time for networking and enjoying snacks and drinks that will be provided.</p> <p>Prof. Dr. Joachim Hornegger, President of Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, will open the event with a welcoming speech.</p> <p>For further information about the event, the panelists, and the moderator, see the event webpage: https://eelisa.eu/events/eelisa-innovation-talk-10-female-innovation/.</p>
Location of the activity (address, if online: link)	ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator and online on the EELISA YouTube Channel: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nbc8TjP-58o .
Type of activity	EELISA Innovation Talk (This event is also reported in EELISA InnoCORE D7.7 as EELISA Innovation Talk # 10.)
Target group	European students, researchers, innovators, and the interested public
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	https://eveeno.com/femaleinnovationtalk (Registration for on-site participation)
Application deadline	None
Date of the activity	3 May 2023
Number of participants	85

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Number of participants from EELISA partners	No data available
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Table 12: “Female Innovation” offered by FAU

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Annex I – Call for the Second EELISA Prototype Contest

**Call for the Second EELISA Prototype Contest:
Win the EELISA Test Space and the EELISA
Co-Creation Workshop at JOSEPHS – The
Open Innovation Lab in Nuremberg, Germany**

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Call for the Second EELISA Prototype Contest:

Win the EELISA Test Space and the EELISA Co-Creation Workshop at JOSEPHS – The Open Innovation Lab in Nuremberg, Germany

Objective

The EELISA innoCORE project pursues the ambitious goal to transform EELISA into the first European University that offers test spaces for prototypes to its startups, researchers, and innovators. To promote this goal, EELISA innoCORE calls for participation in the second EELISA prototype contest. The winning prototype will get an EELISA test space (worth 15,000 €) at JOSEPHS – The Open Innovation Lab in Nuremberg, Germany. Additionally, applicants with the best prototypes (or prototype ideas) from each EELISA partner will win an EELISA co-creation workshop for up to 20 participants with JOSEPHS' open innovation experts. Both, the EELISA test space and the EELISA co-creation workshop will greatly help the selected winners of the contest to create more successful ideas, products, and services.

Proposals with prototypes (or prototype ideas) for the EELISA test space and the EELISA co-creation workshop can be submitted until 27 October 2023 so that the EELISA test space for the winning prototype can be opened at JOSEPHS in December 2023 and the EELISA co-creation workshop for the applicants with the best prototypes (or prototype ideas) from each EELISA partner can take place from 8 to 9 December 2023. For more information about the first EELISA test space at JOSEPHS, watch this short video on EELISA's YouTube channel: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Pq08TYa-A_I.

General information about EELISA, EELISA innoCORE & rationale of the call

- In November 2020, the European University EELISA (European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance) was born. EELISA unites nine universities from seven countries: UPM in Spain, ENPC and PSL in France, SNS and SSSA in Italy, FAU in Germany, BME in Hungary, UPB in Romania, and ITU in Turkey. It thus represents more than 180,000 students, 16,000 faculty members, 11,000 administrative staff, and 50,000 graduates each year. It is EELISA's mission to boost engineering, innovation, and entrepreneurship and to create a model for Europe for solving societal challenges through smart and sustainable solutions. For more information, see <https://eelisa.eu>.
- In June 2021, EELISA innoCORE (INNOvation and COMmon REsearch Strategy) was launched to delve deeper into the institutional transformation initiated by EELISA focusing on the research and innovation dimension of our European University. One of the goals of EELISA innoCORE is to transform the respective innovation ecosystems of all EELISA partners into parts of a much bigger and together even more successful EELISA innovation ecosystem. We will not only bundle the existing innovation activities but also start new ones and build up joint structures. Thus, we will create new opportunities for our startups, researchers, and innovators. For more information, see <https://eelisa.eu/eelisa-innocore/>.
- EELISA innoCORE accentuates the full innovation cycle in order to optimize the outcome of its research activities in cooperation with business and civil society. One important cornerstone for this is JOSEPHS, an open innovation lab in the city center of Nuremberg, Germany. Now, the second EELISA prototype contest will offer an EELISA test space and an EELISA co-creation workshop at JOSEPHS to the EELISA startups, researchers,

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and innovators who want to test their prototypes and learn more about innovation methods. This will not only help our startups, researchers, and innovators to get honest feedback from their potential customers and access to a long-standing expertise in open innovation and co-creation, but also disseminate successful open innovation practices in the EELISA innovation ecosystem and bring about institutional transformation towards a more European innovation ecosystem. Furthermore, it will help our startups to enter the German and European markets and to scale on a European level.

About JOSEPHS - The Open Innovation Lab

JOSEPHS is part of FAU's excellent innovation ecosystem and is unique in its kind in Germany as well as in the EELISA innovation ecosystem. For over nine years, companies and public institutions have been researching and developing new products, services, and business models at JOSEPHS with real users and potential (end) customers. Ideas have been generated, new solutions tested, and further developed in over 160 innovation projects with more than 90,000 visitors. Here are some key facts about JOSEPHS – The Open Innovation Lab:

- Unique methodology and infrastructure for the inclusion of real users and the potential (end) customers in the entire innovation process (researching, developing, testing, marketing)
- Integration of a heterogeneous, unbiased user and (end-)customer group for immediate market feedback
- High-frequency and attractive city center location with over 450 square meters for co-creation and a strong publicity effect
- On-site presentation of innovation projects by specially trained JOSEPHS Innovation Guides during retail opening hours
- Scientifically based, systematic, data-supported development and testing process in a real store environment
- Use of cutting-edge and capital-intensive technologies and service prototyping tools (emotion recognition, virtual reality, 3D design, etc.)
- Inspiring creative and event spaces for co-creative workshops and events (also in hybrid format)
- Competent team of experts and experienced partner network from science and practice
- For more information, see <https://josephs-innovation.de/wp/>.

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Eligible prototypes

Eligible prototypes must fulfill the following criteria:

- Prototypes can be consumer goods, tangible ideas, concepts, or even apps. These prototypes may be physical, digital, or hybrid.
- Prototypes should be of interest to the general public, i.e., to potential customers accessible via Nuremberg's shopping mile. (Note: A prototype whose target group consists exclusively of a very limited group, such as for example business owners, hospital directors, or people with very rare skills or needs, etc., is not eligible.)
- The prototype must be suitable to be tested in English or German.
- The winning prototype must be suitable to be sent to JOSEPHS by mail or by other means. (Note: The winner of the second EELISA prototype contest has to take the responsibility and costs for shipping the winning prototype to JOSEPHS. Shipping costs of up to 250 € can be reimbursed. After the test space period, the prototype will be sent back to the winners by JOSEPHS if it is not heavier than 30 kg and its package dimensions do not exceed 120 x 60 x 60 cm. Otherwise, the winner of the second EELISA prototype contest has to take the responsibility and costs for shipping the winning prototype from JOSEPHS back home. Shipping costs of up to 250 € can be reimbursed.)
- Prototypes should not be heavier than 100 kg, not need more than approximately four square meters of test space, and not be higher than 2 meters.
- Prototypes must be easy and safe to assemble by non-experts without special technical training.
- The setup of prototypes should not require special expertise.
- Prototypes should be operational with regular technical infrastructure (Wi-Fi, electricity, etc.).
- Hazardous goods are not eligible.

Target group

The call is open to startups, researchers, and innovators from all EELISA institutions (including startups founded in the last five years by alumni of EELISA institutions and startups from the following incubators connected to EELISA institutions: actúaupm (UPM), BME U[S]³ (BME), Chimie Paris Innov (PSL), Incubateur Descartes (ENPC), Incubateur Paris-Dauphine (PSL), Innovation Labs (UPB), ITU Cekirdek (ITU), ITU Ginova (ITU), PC Up (PSL), Polo Tecnologico (SNS), Station F (ENPC), ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator (FAU)). Applicants should have a clear intention to develop their prototype (or prototype idea) into a high-quality product ready for successful market entry in Europe. Applications from all disciplines are welcome, with a preferred relation to innovation, technical solutions, and the Sustainable Development Goals. (Note: Winners of the first EELISA prototype contest are not eligible to apply again, in order to give other startups, researchers, and innovators the opportunity to benefit from the contest.)

Timeline

- **Submission deadline: Friday, 27 October 2023**
- Feedback on the winning prototypes: No later than Friday, 10 November 2023

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- Period of the EELISA test space at JOSEPHS: December 2023 until at least January 2024 (kick-off meetings in mid-November 2023, mid-term presentation in mid-December 2023, and feedback report within three weeks after the end of the EELISA test space at JOSEPHS)
- Co-Creation Workshop at JOSEPHS: 8 and 9 December 2023

Evaluation criteria

We welcome short and concise proposals written in English that correspond to the following evaluation criteria:

1. **Suitability of the prototype to be successfully tested at JOSEPHS** (value proposition of the prototype, expected level of interest of the prototype to potential customers or the general public, attractiveness of the prototype, degree of innovation of the prototype, etc.)
2. **Motivation of the applicants to have their prototype tested at JOSEPHS** (potential benefit for the applicants of having their prototype tested at JOSEPHS: feedback from potential customers, data, new ideas, training of AI, etc.)
3. **Prospects for success of the prototype** (likelihood of successful market entry of the prototype, scalability of the prototype, maturity level of the startup or project behind the prototype, etc.)
4. **Contribution of the prototype to the realization of EELISA's mission and vision** (cf. <https://eelisa.eu/what-is-eelisa/>, e. g. contribution to the achievement of the [Sustainable Development Goals](#), link to social responsibility and commitment, fostering gender balance, inclusiveness, and diversity, solving real world problems and mastering global challenges with smart and sustainable solutions, etc.)

If prototypes are eligible up to 10 points can be awarded for each of the four evaluation criteria. The jury will be composed of one expert from each EELISA member and one expert from JOSEPHS. Please see below for the application form.

What you can get

- The winner of the second EELISA prototype contest will get an EELISA test space at JOSEPHS (worth 15,000 €). This will include efficient onboarding and custom fit research design, all-round care by JOSEPHS' innovation specialists, a minimum of one month of actual testing with at least 100 potential customers for 20 minutes each, interim results and adjustments if necessary, a detailed final report with results and impulses for action, honest feedback of your potential customers, an unbiased view from the outside (JOSEPHS as a neutral entity), well-founded facts for internal decision making, access to a long-standing expertise in open innovation and co-creation, and the possibility of white label tests.
- Applicants with the best prototypes (or prototype ideas) from each EELISA partner will win an EELISA co-creation workshop for up to 20 participants with JOSEPHS' open innovation experts. The workshop will be an open innovation and co-creation methods coaching at JOSEPHS (online participation will also be possible) that will take place from 8 to 9 December 2023. The EELISA co-creation workshop will help you to take the next steps towards successful market entry with your prototype and to create more successful ideas, products, and services.
- Note: If your EELISA institution can provide the costs for travel and subsistence, the EELISA test space and the EELISA co-creation workshop at JOSEPHS may be supplemented by an EELISA mobility. In case of being selected by the jury of the second EELISA prototype contest, please contact your local EELISA team to find out more about

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the possibilities of getting travel support.

Application process

Please use [this application form](#) to apply for the call and send the completed document as one PDF to david.schkade@fau.de (and isabel.salgueiro@upm.es in copy) no later than 27 October 2023.

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Annex II – Application Form for the Second EELISA Prototype Contest

Application Form for the Second EELISA Prototype Contest

1. Basic data main applicant (compulsory)

Prototype name:		
Applicant:	Title/First name/Last name:	
	EELISA Institution (or incubator connected to EELISA):	
	Department/Institute/Chair/Study Program:	
	Role (student, staff, researcher, lecturer, professor, alumni (note: alumni must also indicate the month and year their startup was founded), ...)	
	Telephone:	
Email:		

2. Further applicants or team members (optional)

Title/First name/Last name:	EELISA Institution (or incubator connected to EELISA):	Role (Student, staff, researcher, lecturer, professor, alumni (note: alumni must also indicate the month and year of graduation), ...) and department/institute/chair/study program:

Further applicants or team members can be added.

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3. Eligibility criteria (compulsory)

3.1. What kind of product is your prototype (consumer good, tangible idea, app, etc.)?
3.2. Who is the target group of your prototype? (Please answer briefly!)
3.3. Is the prototype suitable to be tested in English or German? (Yes / No)
3.4. What is the size of your prototype (length, width, and height in cm)?
3.5. What is the weight of your prototype (in kg)?
3.6. Is your prototype easy and safe to assemble by non-experts without special technical training? (Yes / No)
3.7. Does the setup of your prototype require special expertise? (Yes / No)
3.8. Is your prototype operational with regular technical infrastructure (Wi-Fi, electricity, etc.)? (Yes / No)
3.9. Is your prototype a hazardous good? (Yes / No)

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4. Evaluation criteria (compulsory)

4.1. Please provide a brief description of your prototype including 1-3 photos!
(Your text should be 250 words maximum.)

4.1.1. First photo of the prototype (compulsory)

4.1.2. Second photo of the prototype (optional)

4.1.3. Third photo of the prototype (optional)

4.2. What is your motivation to have your prototype tested at JOSEPHS?
(Your text should be 250 words maximum.)

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4.3. Please give a brief assessment of the prospects for market success of your prototype including a brief description of the stage of your startup or project!

(Your text should be 500 words maximum.)

4.4. What contribution does your prototype make to the realization of EELISA's mission and vision?

(Your text should be 250 words maximum.)

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